

Breaking the Barrier: CPR in Action Conservative Canal Preparation & Ultrasonic Retrieval in Molar Canals - A Case Series

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Abstract

Introduction: Instrument separation during root canal treatment is a recognized procedural complication that may compromise canal debridement and treatment outcome. Management depends on the location of the fragment, with coronal third fragments showing higher success rates for conservative approaches such as bypass and ultrasonic retrieval.

Case Presentation: Two clinical cases with separated instruments in the coronal third of molar canals are presented. Both patients had a history of previously initiated root canal treatment. Radiographic examination confirmed the presence of fractured instruments obstructing canal access. After achieving isolation and access refinement, bypass was successfully performed using #8 and #10 K-files to establish canal patency and glide path. This was followed by ultrasonic activation using the Endo-X ultrasonic system under continuous sodium hypochlorite irrigation, which facilitated safe retrieval of the fragments. Subsequent biomechanical preparation was completed using rotary instrumentation, followed by obturation and post-endodontic restoration.

Conclusion: The combination of bypass technique and ultrasonic retrieval provides a conservative, effective, and predictable approach for managing separated instruments in the coronal third. This method preserves radicular dentin and enables successful completion of endodontic therapy.

Keywords: Separated instrument, Endodontic complication, Ultrasonic retrieval, Endo-X ultrasonic system, Bypass technique, Root canal treatment.

Introduction

Instrument separation during root canal treatment is a recognized procedural complication that may compromise the outcome of endodontic therapy. The reported incidence ranges between 2% and 6% of cases, influenced by factors such as canal anatomy, operator experience, instrumentation technique, and the type of instrument used⁽¹⁾. The presence of a fractured instrument within the canal may obstruct access to the apical region, thereby preventing adequate cleaning, shaping, and disinfection, ultimately affecting treatment prognosis⁽²⁾.

Instrument separation may occur due to torsional stress, cyclic fatigue, excessive reuse of instruments, inadequate glide path preparation, and complex root canal anatomy. Stainless steel instruments generally fail due to torsional overload, whereas nickel titanium (NiTi) rotary instruments are more prone to cyclic fatigue, particularly in curved canals⁽²⁾. Management of separated instruments requires careful clinical decision making, with

options including retrieval, bypassing, or leaving the fragment in situ. The choice depends on factors such as the location of the fragment, canal curvature, stage of instrumentation, and the presence of periapical pathology⁽³⁾. Among these, the bypass technique is considered a conservative and predictable approach, allowing negotiation around the fragment with small hand files to regain working length and complete chemomechanical preparation⁽⁴⁾.

The location of the fractured fragment plays a crucial role in determining treatment outcomes. Fragments located in the coronal third generally demonstrate higher retrieval success due to better accessibility and visibility, whereas those in the apical third present greater challenges^(1,5).

Quick Response Code

Submitted 29 April 2026
Accepted 09 May 2026
Published 12 June 2026

Access this Article Online

Website: www.healtalk.in

DOI

How to Cite This Article : Palakal et al. -

In recent years, ultrasonic techniques have gained widespread acceptance for the management of separated instruments, as they allow controlled dentin removal and generate micro-vibrations that help loosen the fragment while preserving surrounding dentin^(6,7). A key advancement in this context is the concept of CPR (Conservative Canal Preparation & Retrieval), which emphasizes minimal and strategic dentin removal to achieve straight line access while preserving root integrity. It involves selective dentin troughing around the coronal aspect of the fragment using ultrasonic tips under magnification, facilitating safe exposure and mobilization of the separated instrument.

In the present cases, ultrasonic retrieval was performed using the Endo-X ultrasonic activator (Waldent, India), which enables controlled dentin removal and effective troughing around the fragment. Its high frequency vibrations aid in loosening the instrument while preserving surrounding dentin, supporting a minimally invasive approach.

The present article reports two clinical cases of separated instruments located in the coronal third of molar canals, highlighting the effectiveness of combining bypass techniques with CPR-guided ultrasonic retrieval as a conservative and predictable management strategy.

Case 1

A 38 years old female patient named Rashmi reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics at Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and research centre with the chief complaint of pain in relation to lower right back tooth region for the past 2 weeks. The patient's medical history was non-contributory.

Patient history revealed a previously attempted root canal treatment in relation to the concerned tooth at another clinic, 4 months back. On Clinical examination showed RCT was initiated on right lower molar. Intraoral periapical radiograph (IOPA) revealed a separated instrument at the radiopaque fragment consistent with a separated endodontic instrument located in the coronal third of the mesio buccal and distal canal of the involved molar tooth. The fragment appeared lodged within the cervical position, obstructing access to the middle and apical third portion of the canals. There was no periapical radiolucency or periapical changes were associated with the tooth.

Fig 1a: Pre Operative Radiograph with Separated Instruments In Both Mesial and Distal Canal

Considering the location of the fragment in the coronal third of the canals, a conservative approach involving bypass of the separated instruments followed by ultrasonic retrieval using the Endo-X ultrasonic system was planned.

After administration of local anesthesia, the tooth was isolated with a rubber dam to maintain proper isolation and aseptic conditions. The access cavity was refined to obtain straight-line access to the root canal system.

Initial attempts were made to negotiate the canals using #8 and #10 K-files. Successful bypass of the separated instrument fragments was achieved using these small stainless-steel hand files, which helped in establishing canal patency and a preliminary glide path.

During subsequent irrigation and ultrasonic activation around the coronal portion of the separated fragments using the Waldent Endo-X ultrasonic system, the fractured instrument segments were dislodged and retrieved from the canals. Continuous irrigation with sodium hypochlorite was maintained throughout the procedure to facilitate debris removal and prevent overheating.

Following successful retrieval of the separated fragments, working length was determined. Canal negotiation was then performed using #8 and #10 K-files to establish patency and create a smooth glide path.

Subsequently, biomechanical preparation was carried out using the Dentsply ProTaper rotary system under copious irrigation with sodium hypochlorite. The mesial canals were prepared up to size F2, while the distal canal was prepared up to size F3 to ensure adequate cleaning and shaping of the root canal system.

FIG 1b: Intraoral periapical showing a clear mesio buccal and distal canal

FIG 1c: Retrieved instrument

The canals were then thoroughly irrigated and dried with sterile paper points. Master cone fit was confirmed radiographically, following which Obturation was completed using gutta-percha and sealer by the single cone technique, followed by

placement of a post endodontic composite restoration to restore the access cavity.

Fig 1d: Master Cone

Fig 1e: Obturation and Post Endo

Case 2

A 48 years old female patient named Shahn reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics at Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre with the chief complaint of pain in relation to upper right back tooth region for the past 10 days. The patient's medical history was non-contributory.

The patient's history revealed that root canal treatment had been initiated in relation to the same tooth at another clinic approximately four months earlier. On clinical examination, it was observed that root canal treatment had been initiated in relation to the upper right molar. An intraoral periapical radiograph (IOPA) demonstrated a radiopaque fragment suggestive of a separated endodontic instrument in the coronal third of the distobuccal canal of the affected molar. The fragment appeared lodged within the canal, thereby obstructing access to the apical portion of the canal. No periapical radiolucency or other periapical changes were observed in relation to the tooth.

Fig 2a: Pre Operative Radiograph with Separated Instruments

After administration of local anesthesia, the access cavity was refined to obtain straight-line access to the root canal system.

FIG 2b: Radiograph showing successful bypass of the separated instrument.

Initial attempts were made to negotiate the canals using small stainless-steel hand files, and successful bypass of the separated instrument fragment was achieved using #8 and #10 K-files, establishing canal patency and a preliminary glide path.

During subsequent irrigation and ultrasonic activation around the coronal portion of the separated fragment using the Waldent Endo-X ultrasonic system, the fragment was dislodged and retrieved from the distobuccal canal. Continuous irrigation with sodium hypochlorite was maintained throughout the procedure to facilitate debris removal and prevent overheating. Canal patency was then reconfirmed.

Following successful retrieval, biomechanical preparation was carried out using Endostar rotary files under copious irrigation with sodium hypochlorite. The mesiobuccal and distobuccal canals were prepared up to size 25/.04, while the palatal canal was prepared up to size 30/.04 to ensure adequate cleaning and shaping of the root canal system.

The canals were then thoroughly irrigated and dried with sterile paper points. Master cone fit was confirmed radiographically, following which Obturation was completed using gutta-percha and sealer by the single cone technique, followed by placement of a post-endodontic composite restoration to restore the access cavity.

Fig 2c: Obturation of the Canal after Removal of Separated Instruments

Discussion

Instrument separation during root canal treatment is a recognized procedural complication that may interfere with adequate cleaning and shaping of the root canal system. The reported incidence of separated endodontic instruments ranges between 2% and 6% of endodontic procedures, depending on factors such as canal anatomy, operator experience, and instrumentation technique^(1,6). The presence of a fractured instrument within the canal may obstruct access to the apical portion of the root canal and potentially compromise treatment outcomes if proper debridement cannot be achieved^(2,3).

The fracture of endodontic instruments may occur due to torsional stress, cyclic fatigue, excessive reuse of instruments, and complex root canal anatomy^(2,6). Nickel titanium rotary instruments are particularly susceptible to cyclic fatigue caused by repeated tension compression cycles during rotation in curved canals⁽⁹⁾. The location of the fractured fragment plays a significant role in determining the prognosis and management strategy. Studies have reported that approximately 15–25% of separated instruments occur in the coronal third of the canal, whereas the majority occur in the middle and apical thirds where canal curvature and mechanical stress are greater^(5,8).

Several treatment options have been suggested for the management of separated instruments, including instrument retrieval, bypassing the fragment, leaving the fragment in situ, or surgical intervention when nonsurgical methods fail^(3,7). The decision depends on factors such as the position of the fragment, canal curvature, presence of periapical pathology, and stage of instrumentation⁽⁷⁾. Fragments located in the coronal third of the canal generally have a higher probability of successful retrieval, with reported success rates ranging from 80% to 95%, because they are more accessible and require minimal dentin removal compared with fragments located beyond the canal curvature or in the apical third^(5,8,10).

The bypass technique is considered a conservative and effective approach for managing separated instruments. By negotiating small hand files alongside the fractured fragment, canal patency can be re-established and a glide path can be created for further instrumentation⁽⁴⁾. In the present cases, #8 and #10 K-files were successfully used to bypass the fragments, which allowed the establishment of a glide path and facilitated subsequent canal preparation.

Ultrasonic techniques have been widely recommended for the retrieval of separated instruments because they allow controlled dentin removal and precise vibration around the fractured fragment^(6,8). Ultrasonic activation produces high frequency vibrations that help loosen the fragment from the surrounding dentinal walls while preserving radicular dentin. Additionally, ultrasonic activation produces acoustic streaming and cavitation effects within the irrigating solution, improving debris removal and visualization within the root canal system⁽⁶⁾.

In the present cases, the Endo-X ultrasonic system was used following successful bypass of the fragments. Ultrasonic activation around the coronal portion of the fragments facilitated their

dislodgement from the canal walls and enabled their retrieval with minimal dentin removal. Because the fragments were located in the coronal third of the canals, retrieval was achieved without excessive removal of surrounding dentin, thereby reducing the risk of complications such as perforation or excessive weakening of the root structure.

Both cases demonstrate that a combined approach of bypassing the fragment followed by ultrasonic activation provides a conservative and predictable method for the management of separated instruments located in the coronal third of root canals. This approach allows preservation of radicular dentin, minimizes procedural complications, and facilitates successful completion of endodontic treatment.

Conclusion

Separated instruments can compromise root canal treatment by obstructing adequate cleaning and shaping of the canal. The present cases demonstrate that bypass using small hand files followed by ultrasonic activation with the Endo-X system can effectively retrieve fragments located in the coronal third of the canal. This conservative approach helps preserve radicular dentin and allows successful completion of endodontic therapy.

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